

1-Lyso-2-arachidonoyl-phosphatidate (LPA)

Mann-Whitney test: p -value < 0,0001

Cohen's D: 1,3519

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.9815

False positive risk: 9×10^{-04}

N-Docosahexaenoyl GABA

Mann-Whitney test: p -value < 0,0001

Cohen's D: 0.9452

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.8075910

False positive risk: 0.0015

Vanillic acid

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0049

Cohen's D: 1.1494240

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.9305652

False positive risk: 0.0465

Ferulic acid

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0.0097

Cohen's D: 1.2181

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.9540

False positive risk: 0.1289

3-O-Methyl-a-methyldopa

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0164

Cohen's D: 1.3151

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.9759

False positive risk: 0.3431

Hypoxanthine

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0001

Cohen's D: 0.8191

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.6886

False positive risk: 0.0025

Chenodeoxycholic acid glycine conjugate $[M-H]^+$

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0.0004

Cohen's D: 0.8756

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.7926

False positive risk: 0.0043

Caffeine

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0081

Cohen's D: 0.7885

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.6555

False positive risk: 0.0539

2-trans,4-cis-Decadienoylcarnitine

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0146

Cohen's D: 0.7000

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.5539

False positive risk: 0.0895

Pipecolic acid

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0072

Cohen's D: 0.6973

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.5507

False positive risk: 0.054

Paraxanthine

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0343

Cohen's D: 0.5980

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.4327

False positive risk: 0.1726

15(S)-HETE

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0204

Cohen's D: 0.4924

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.3139

False positive risk: 0.1472

Taurodeoxycholic acid

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0.0017

Cohen's D: 0.2741

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.1300

False positive risk: 0.1594

12-KETE

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0,0277

Cohen's D: 0.4933

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.3148

False positive risk: 0.1717

15(S)-HPETE

Mann-Whitney test: p -value = 0.0459

Cohen's D: 0.6876

Power post-hoc ($1 - \beta$ err prob): 0.5398

False positive risk: 0.2114

